

A Hypothetical Source of Dark Matter: Fragmentation and Clustering of Black Hole Remnants Following a Universal Eruption

Abstract

This hypothesis proposes that a *Universal Eruption* of a supermassive black hole (Rao, 2024) could lead to the fragmentation of its material into smaller black holes, ranging from stellar to intermediate masses. These fragmented black holes, dispersed throughout the universe, might gravitationally interact with emerging cosmic structures. Rather than accreting all nearby baryonic matter, these black holes could cluster and act as gravitational seeds, influencing galaxy formation. We suggest that these primordial black holes (PBHs), remnants of the eruption, could constitute a significant portion of dark matter. Since PBHs do not emit detectable electromagnetic radiation, their gravitational effects could account for the missing mass inferred from cosmic observations, potentially offering an alternative explanation for dark matter.

Background

The Role of Dark Matter

Dark matter is a cornerstone of modern cosmology, introduced to explain the "missing mass" in galaxies and clusters. Without it, the gravitational forces of visible matter alone cannot account for the observed rotation curves of galaxies or the degree of gravitational lensing observed in cosmic structures. Despite its significance, dark matter remains undetectable by electromagnetic means, which has led to the ongoing search for its true nature. One of the more speculative candidates is primordial black holes (PBHs), which could form under certain conditions and provide the necessary gravitational influence without the need for exotic new particles.

Current Primordial Black Hole (PBH) Models

Traditional PBH models (Zel'dovich & Novikov, 1967) suggest that these black holes formed in the early universe due to density fluctuations. Small over-dense regions in the hot, rapidly expanding universe may have collapsed under their own gravity, forming black holes. This model ties PBHs to the Big Bang and positions them as relics of the universe's early moments. These PBHs would have masses ranging from sub-stellar to tens of solar masses and could contribute to dark matter without requiring modification of the standard cosmological model.

Revised Model: PBHs from a Universal Eruption

The *Universal Eruption* hypothesis introduces a new pathway for the formation of PBHs. In this framework, the Observable Universe (OU) originates from the explosive eruption of a supermassive black hole, releasing the matter and energy confined within its event horizon. During this eruption, the ejected material could fragment into smaller black holes, spanning a wide mass range, rather than uniformly dispersing. These smaller black holes, formed from the remnants of the supermassive progenitor, would be scattered across the universe, and their gravitational influence could be key to shaping cosmic structures.

Unlike standard PBH models, which tie the formation of these objects to early universe conditions following the Big Bang, this revised model connects PBHs directly to the *Universal Eruption*, suggesting they are remnants of material once confined within a primordial

supermassive black hole. This scenario provides an alternative to the density fluctuation-driven collapse model, proposing that the ejected material fragmented into PBHs as part of the eruptive process.

Quantity and Distribution of Black Holes

Recent gravitational wave detections from experiments such as LIGO and Virgo have revealed black holes with masses higher than those predicted by stellar evolution models. For instance, black holes exceeding 50 solar masses challenge the standard models because massive stars tend to lose a significant amount of mass through stellar winds before collapsing into black holes. This has raised questions about the origin of such large black holes and whether other mechanisms, such as the collapse of primordial material or alternative formation processes, could explain their existence.

A *Universal Eruption* could naturally result in a population of black holes with varying masses, depending on the dynamics of the eruption and the distribution of the fragmented material. These black holes would differ from those formed in stellar evolution or early universe density fluctuations, offering a unique origin scenario. Additionally, this model could account for the observed abundance of black holes, including those detected via gravitational waves, without requiring new formation mechanisms.

The clustering of these black holes could further influence the evolution of galaxies and cosmic structures, as their gravitational interactions with surrounding matter might enhance structure formation, providing seeds for galaxy formation in the early universe. The coexistence of these black holes with baryonic matter ejected during the *Universal Eruption* suggests that both types of material share a common origin, a scenario consistent with the dynamics of large-scale cosmic evolution.

Dark Matter Implications

If PBHs formed from the remnants of a supermassive black hole eruption, they would likely be distributed across the universe in ways that make direct detection difficult. However, their gravitational effects could account for the unseen mass that dark matter is invoked to explain. This hypothesis suggests that dark matter could be composed, at least in part, of these PBHs, whose non-interacting nature (in terms of electromagnetic forces) makes them invisible except through their gravitational influence.

The idea that dark matter could consist of PBHs is not new, but this revised scenario provides a new formation mechanism that ties the presence of dark matter to a specific cosmic event. Unlike models that rely on exotic new particles, this hypothesis remains within the framework of general relativity and black hole physics, offering a simpler, albeit speculative, explanation for dark matter.

Conclusion

The *Universal Eruption* hypothesis provides an alternative framework for understanding both the origin of PBHs and the nature of dark matter. If the remnants of a supermassive black hole

explosion fragmented into smaller black holes, these objects could cluster and evolve alongside galaxies, acting as gravitational anchors in the formation of cosmic structures. These PBHs, being electromagnetically dark, may constitute a significant portion of the universe's dark matter, offering a viable explanation for the missing mass problem. While speculative, this idea is compatible with gravitational observations and opens new avenues for investigating the role of black holes in cosmic evolution.

References

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Zel'dovich, Y. B., & Novikov, I. D. (1967). *The Hypothesis of Cores Retarded During Expansion and the Hot Cosmological Model*. *Soviet Astronomy – AJ*, 10, 602.